

D6.10

Presence of pesticide residues in olive oil

Date: 28th December 2024

Version: 2

**Funded by
the European Union**

SOIL O-LIVE (Grant Agreement ID: 101091255) is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EIC. Neither the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

D6.10 Presence of pesticide residues in olive oil

Document Information

Project title	SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work package	WP6 – Ecosystem Services
Deliverable number and title	D6.10 Presence of pesticide residues in olive oil
Deliverable description	D6.10 Report on the presence of pesticide residues in olive oil samples from selected olive groves (intermediate). (T6.5.)
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	PU
Lead beneficiary	UJA
Due submission date	31 December 2023 (M12)
Submission date	28 December 2024

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Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
V2	28.12.2024	Andrés J. Rascón	Correction of data due to a sample mislabeling. Sample numbers revised and corrected, as requested in Review Report Figures 1 – 3 Figure key amended as requested in Review Report
V1	31.01.2024	Andrés J. Rascón	Initial Report

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.10 reports on the work developed under task 6.5 “Evaluation of the presence of pesticide residues in olive oil from olive groves” during the Diagnostic pre-operational stage of SOIL O-LIVE project (first 18 months). The data obtained is used in conjunction with other variables to assess the agroecosystem functionality in the selected olive orchards. The ultimate goal is to understand the relationship between farming practices, soil health and olive oil quality and safety. To this aim, the present document describes the results obtained in the analysis of pesticides performed on the obtained virgin olive oils from the selected orchards from different soil management systems: traditional (TD), high-density (HD) and organic (ORG) cultivars.

This study requires the application of two different analytical methods: one multiresidue method including a list of 60 herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides; and a specific method for the analysis of the herbicide glyphosate and its main metabolite, aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA). Methods are described in detail in document D6.9 “ Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)”, and summarized in section 2 of this document. Briefly, liquid-liquid extraction with an appropriate solvent was performed before the analysis by Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS).

A total of 41 samples were received out of the 52 different orchards from Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece. The lower production in the 2023 olive harvest season made it impossible to get samples from all orchards. Virgin olive oil was received only from 11 orchards, while olive oil production was performed at a laboratory scale through an Abencor® system for the remaining 30 orchards (which delivered frozen olives to the laboratory of analysis). Olive samples from two orchards from an experiment using biochar were also processed and analysed.

All samples tested negative for glyphosate and AMPA residues, which do not accumulate in the olive oil because they are hydrophilic compounds. For the multiresidue analysis of pesticides, some differences were observed based on the soil management practice. Of these, oils from high-density orchards showed the highest levels of contamination, with those from traditional following closely behind. As expected, oils derived from organically managed soils exhibited the lowest contamination levels. The most frequently identified contaminants were fungicides, including difenoconazole, myclobutanil, pyraclostrobin, and trifloxystrobin. The herbicide diflufenican was also present. The presence of fungicides may be expected given their direct application to crops. Difenoconazole, myclobutanil, and pyraclostrobin were also identified in the organic managed olive oils. Pesticides are dynamic in the environment, settling into soil and plants and being spread by factors such as rain and wind. Although organic soils generally contain fewer pesticides than conventionally managed ones, residual contamination can still impact products due to these environmental dynamics.

Table of Acronyms

AMPA - Aminomethylphosphonic acid

d-SPE – Dispersive solid-phase extraction

ES – Spain

EU – European Union

GR – Greece

HD – High-density

IS – Internal Standard

IT – Italy

LoQ – Limits of quantification

MR – Morocco

MRL – Maximum Residue Level

MS – Mass spectrometry

ORG- Organic

PT – Portugal

QuEChERS - Quick, Easy, Clean, Effective, Rugged and Safe

TD – Traditional

UHPLC – Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This report is intended to reveal the findings of evaluating pesticide residue levels in specified orchards. The assessment covered three distinct cultivation methods: traditional, high-density, and organic agriculture. The testing procedures conducted are detailed in the document *D6.9 Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)*. The aim of this study is to analyse the presence of pesticides and related compounds in the produced oils.

1.2 Sampling

Out of the 52 olive orchards of the project, 41 samples from the different orchards were received from Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece (see table 1). The three different type of land management were: Traditional (TD), High-Density (HD), and Organic (ORG). Additionally, two samples were received from orchards where the soil was treated with biochar, discussed in a separate section.

Table 1. List of olive orchards from which olive oil samples were received

Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD-01 Control	ES-HD-2	ES-ORG-4
ES-TD-01 Biochar*	ES-HD-3	ES-ORG-6
ES-TD-05 Control	ES-HD-8	ES-ORG-11
ES-TD-05 Biochar*	ES-HD-22	ES-ORG-12
ES-TD-07	ES-HD-40	ES-ORG-13
ES-TD-09	GR-HD-43	ES-ORG-14
ES-TD-15	MR-HD-25	GR-ORG-32
IT-TD-20	PT-HD-51	GR-ORG-33
IT-TD-50	PT-HD-52	GR-ORG-34
MR-TD-24	PT-HD-53	GR-ORG-45
MR-TD-26		GR-ORG-47
MR-TD-27		IT-ORG-18
MR-TD-28		IT-ORG-19
MR-TD-29		PT-ORG-42**
GR-TD-30		
GR-TD-31		
GR-TD-44		
GR-TD-46		
PT-TD-41		

*Biochar samples from the selected orchards will be compared in Section 3.2.

** Due to a mislabelling the sample in the previous version of this document was classified as PT-TD-42.

In summary, 79% of the expected samples have been received, as it is following detailed:

- Morocco – 6 olive oil samples out of 7 (**86 % of the expected samples**)

- Spain – 16 olive samples out of 16 have been received (**100 % of the expected samples**)
- Greece – 5 Oils and 5 olives out of 15 have been received (**75 % of the expected samples**)
- Portugal – 5 olive samples received (**100 % of the expected samples**)
- Italy – 4 olive samples out of 9 have been received (**44 % of the expected samples**)

From 11 orchards, olive oil was received, while raw fruit (olives) was received from the 30 remaining orchards. Unprocessed olives were got, too, from the orchards with biochar treatment. To obtain olive oil at laboratory scale, the samples were processed using the ABENCOR procedure for olive oil extraction described in document *D6.12 Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines* (malaxation: 30 °C, 30 min, no talc addition). This procedure has certain limitations related to the olive oil that we can produce per working day, and to the absence of food contact standard procedures that ensure that the final product may be considered as edible oil (see document D6.13).

2. Experimental

To isolate and quantify the presence of pesticides and related compounds in oils, two different analytical methods have been employed. One method focuses on the extraction and detection of glyphosate and its main metabolite -AMPA- from oils, while the other is a multiresidue method for multiclass pesticides in oils. Glyphosate and AMPA (aminomethylphosphonic acid) are not included in the latter multiresidue method because of their distinct physicochemical properties, mainly their high polarity compared to the rest of studied pesticides. The analytical methods followed are the detailed ones in document *D6.9 Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)*, with small modifications.

2.1 Glyphosate and AMPA in oils

The analysis of glyphosate and AMPA was conducted following the method by Chiarello et al.¹ with minor modifications a liquid-liquid extraction procedure as sample treatment preceding a chromatographic analysis with mass spectrometric detection. Briefly, 10 g of oil sample were extracted using a solution of 0.1% aqueous formic acid. After vigorous shaking and centrifugation, the supernatant was transferred to a plastic vial for analysis.

Chromatographic separation and quantification were performed using Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) coupled with a hybrid quadrupole-linear ion trap triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (AB Sciex). The UHPLC was equipped with an Anionic Polar Pesticide column (5 µm, 2.1 x 100 mm). The column was initially equilibrated with a mixture of water and acetonitrile, both containing 0.1% formic acid, in a ratio of 90:10. Detection followed optimized parameters for each analyte, determined through individual infusion into the mass spectrometer.

The analytical parameters summarized in Table 2:

Table 2. Analytical parameters of the method for glyphosate and AMPA

Recoveries	81 - 96 %
Precision (RSD)	1.5 - 7.0 %
Linear range	0.5 – 50 µg/kg
Limits of quantification (LoQ)	0.5 µg/kg

2.2 Multiresidue analysis for pesticides in oils

The detection of pesticides in oil samples was conducted using a modified QuEChERS procedure. In this method, the sample underwent extraction with acetonitrile (3 g of sample per analysis). Subsequently, a dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) was performed using EMR-Lipid sorbent for extract clean-up. This process was complemented by the addition of commercially available anhydrous MgSO₄ to remove residual water and any water-soluble residues. Finally, the resulting extract underwent filtration.

The pesticide profile of each sample was determined using UHPLC coupled with a high-resolution mass spectrometer (Q-Exactive, Thermo). The Vanquish UHPLC, equipped with a Zorbax Eclipse plus C18 column (4.6 x 50 mm, 1.8 µm particle size), operated at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The column was equilibrated with a water:methanol mixture (95:5). Detection followed the optimal parameters for each analyte, obtained through their individual infusion into the mass spectrometer.

The list of pesticides included in the method is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. List of pesticides included in the multiresidue method.

Target compounds		
Atrazine	Dimoxystrobin	Oxyfluorfen
Atrazine desethyl	Diuron	Parathion
Atrazine desisopropyl	Epoxiconazole	Parathion-methyl
Boscalid	Ethion	Penconazole
Bromuconazole (2 isomers)	Fenpropidine	Pirimicarb
Carbaryl	Flufenacet	Prochloraz
Carbendazim	Fluquinconazole	Propiconazole
Carbofuran	Fluroxypyr	Prosulfocarb
Chloridazon (Pyrazon)	Imazalil	Pyraclostrobin
Chlorpyrifos ethyl	Imazamox	Quinoxifen
Chlorpyrifos methyl	Imidacloprid	Simazine
Clothianidin	Isoproturon	Terbutylazine
Cymoxanil	Isoxaben	Terbutryn
Cyproconazole	Lenacil	Thiabendazole
Cyprodinil	Linuron	Thiophanate-methyl
Desethyl-terbutylazine	Malathion	Triadimenol
Difenoconazole	Metalaxyl	Triallat
Diflufenican	Metamitron	Trifloxystrobin
Dimethenamid	Metolachlor	
Dimethomorph (E + Z isomers)	Myclobutanil	
<i>Caffeine-13C (IS)*</i>		

* Caffeine-13C was used as Internal Standard (IS)

The methodology provided the analytical parameters summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Analytical parameters

Recoveries	75 – 105 %
Precision (RSD)	1.0 – 10 %
Linear range	0.10 – 100 µg/kg
LOQ < 10 µg/kg for 98 % of target compounds*	

**The “Guidance Document on Pesticide Analytical Methods for Risk Assessment and Post-approval Control and Monitoring Purposes” (SANTE/2020/12830, Rev.2) states that “for monitoring methods, the validated LOQ of residue analytical methods should generally be at the default MRL of 0.01 mg/kg for plant and animal commodities”.*

3. Results

3.1 Glyphosate and AMPA analysis

The different oils obtained following the Operating Standard Procedure *D6.9 Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)* with slight modifications.

All the received samples from the different types of soil management were analysed under the described conditions. None of the analysed samples showed a positive result for these two compounds as displayed in Table 5. Currently, a maximum residue level (MRL) of 1 mg/kg is set for glyphosate in olives for oil production². Thus, even without considering a processing factor for olive oil (which may be a multiplier around 3-4 times the MRL set for olives)³, the results show that the obtained oils from the selected orchards comply with current EU regulations.

Table 5. Glyphosate and AMPA results by type of soil management

	TD	HD	ORG
Compound ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)			
Glyphosate	N.D.*	N.D.	N.D.
AMPA	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.

* N.D.: not detected.

Glyphosate and its derivatives are polar molecules, meaning they are hydrophilic and not soluble in oils such as olive oil. Consequently, their presence can be considered negligible, since they are diverted to the aqueous waste phase during olive oil production in olive mills (López-Blanco *et al.*, 2018)⁴. Part of the potential content is also washed from the surface of olives with water prior to the production process

3.2 Multiresidue analysis for pesticides in olive oil

The pesticides selected for his study are under the Regulation of the European Union for their presence in olives and olives intended for oil production, as can be seen in the European Pesticide Database⁵. The detected compounds did not exceed the Maximum Residue Levels (MRL) set by the mentioned Regulation.

3.2.1 Oils from Traditional orchards

A total of 14 samples and 2 biochar samples from traditionally managed land were tested under the specified conditions. Among these, 4 (+2 biochar) samples were from Spanish orchards, 4 from Greece, 2 from Italy, 3 from Morocco, and 1 from Portugal. Overall, out of the 60 pesticides included in the analytical method, a total of 14 were detected in at least one sample. Results per country and type of land management are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Distribution of positives and concentration in oils from traditional managed orchards

	No of samples	No of positives (% of positives)				Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
		0	1	2 – 5	> 6		
ES	4	- (-)	2 (50 %)	2 (50 %)	0 (-)	0.20	0.20 – 2.6
GR	4	- (-)	- (-)	4 (100 %)		0.33	0.22 – 19
IT	2	1 (50 %)	1 (50 %)	- (-)		0.53	0 – 0.53
MR	3	1 (33 %)	1 (33 %)	1 (33 %)		0.47	0 – 7.0
PT	1	- (-)	1 (100 %)	- (-)		0.17	0.17
Global data	14	2 (14 %)	5 (36 %)	7 (50 %)		0.33	0 – 19

Upon examining the different samples per country and the occurrence of positive detections within them, it was found that 2 out of 14 samples were free of pesticides (representing the 14 % of the samples), while 5 of them contained one positive result (36 %) and 7 samples were in the range of 2 to 5 pesticides detected (50 %). In any case the samples contained more than 5 pesticides. In general terms, the median concentration of each individual pesticide detected in TD oils is 0.33 µg/kg, within a concentration range of 0 to 19 µg/kg. The distribution by percentage is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig 1. Olive oil samples (TD soil management) with detected pesticides, arranged by country, and percentage of different detected compounds per sample

When considering different countries, 50% of the samples from Spain (2 samples) contained 1 pesticide, while the remaining 50% (2 samples) contained 2 to 5 pesticides. The median concentration was 0.20 µg/kg, and the samples ranged from 0.20 to 2.6 µg/kg. All four Greek samples (100%) fell within the 2 to 5 range of pesticide detection rate. The samples ranged from 0.22 to 19 µg/kg, showing the highest overall concentration among the TD oil samples. The two Italian samples were evenly split, with 50% showing no detected pesticides and 50% showing 1 detected pesticide. The three Moroccan samples were equally distributed: 33% with 0 pesticides detected, 33% with 1 pesticide detected, and 33% with 2 to 5 pesticides detected with a median value of 0.17 µg/kg and a concentration range of 0 to 7 µg/kg. The Portuguese sample showed the presence of 1 pesticide (100 %) with a concentration value of 0.17 µg/kg.

The most detected active substances were **difenoconazole**, **myclobutanil**, **pyraclostrobin**, and **trifloxystrobin**, which are fungicides, along with **diflufenican**, an herbicide, respectively. The presence of fungicides can be expected as they are applied directly over the crops, while the presence of herbicides and pesticides can be caused by dust, soil and environmental cross-contamination. The tested pesticides are regulated by the European Commission for their presence in olives and olives intended for oil production, as can be seen in the European Pesticide Database⁵. The median value for difenoconazole detected was 0.50 µg/kg, 0.49 µg/kg for myclobutanil, 0.19 µg/kg for pyraclostrobin, and 0.23 µg/kg for trifloxystrobin. These values are far **below the limits** set by the mentioned Regulation, which are 2000 µg/kg, 10 µg/kg, 20 µg/kg, and 300 µg/kg, respectively. Diflufenican was detected at a median value of 0.49 µg/kg, significantly lower than the limit specified in the Regulation, which is 600 µg/kg.

Finally, when comparing the control samples to the ones from the biochar experiment, there were no significant differences between them in terms of pesticide presence and concentration. One sample contained 1 pesticide (diflufenican) at 0.18 µg/kg and the other one was free of pesticides.

3.2.2 Oils from High-density orchards

A total of 10 samples from high density managed land were tested under the specified conditions. Among these, 5 samples were from Spanish orchards, 1 from Greece, 1 from Morocco, and 3 from Portugal. Overall, out of the 60 pesticides included in the analytical method, a total of 9 were detected in at least one sample. Results per country and type of land management are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Distribution of positives and concentration in oils from high-density managed orchards

	No of samples	No of positives (% of positives)				Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
		0	1	2 – 5	> 6		
ES	5	- (-)	3 (60 %)	2 (40 %)	0 (-)	1.50	0.11 – 20
GR	1	- (-)	- (-)	1 (100 %)		0.21	0.12 – 1.30
MR	1	1 (100 %)	- (-)	- (-)		-	-
PT	3	- (-)	2 (67 %)	1 (33 %)		0.41	0.15 – 18
Global data	10	1 (11 %)	5 (56 %)	3 (33 %)		0.33	0 – 20

Upon examining the different samples and the occurrence of positive detections within them, it was found that only one out of ten samples was free of pesticides (representing 11% of the samples), while five of them contained at least one positive result (56%), and three samples were in the range of 2 to 5 pesticides detected (33%). No sample contained more than 5 pesticides. In general terms, the median concentration of an individual pesticide detected in HD oils is 0.33 µg/kg, within a concentration range of 0 to 20 µg/kg. The distribution by percentage is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig 2. Olive oil samples (HD soil management) with detected pesticides, arranged by country, and percentage of different detected compounds per sample

The Spanish samples contained a median of 1.50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, and a concentration range of 0.11 – 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Three of the samples (60%) contained 1 pesticide, while two samples (40%) fell within the 2 to 5 range. The only Greek sample fell within the 2 to 5 interval of pesticide detection. None of the selected pesticides were detected in the Moroccan sample, whereas for the Portuguese samples two of them (67%) contained 1 pesticide, and one sample (33%) contained 2 to 5 pesticides, with a median value of 0.41 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

The most detected compounds were **difenoconazole**, and **trifloxystrobin**, which are fungicides, along with the herbicide **diflufenican**. As mentioned before, the presence of fungicides can be expected, while the presence of herbicides may be caused by cross-contamination. The tested pesticides are regulated by European Commission for their presence in olives and olives intended for oil production, as can be seen in the European Pesticide Database⁵. The median values for difenoconazole detection were 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, and for trifloxystrobin, it was 0.23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. These figures remain comfortably **below the limits** outlined in the Regulation, which are 2000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively. Diflufenican was detected at a median value of 1.30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, significantly lower than the regulatory threshold of 600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

3.2.3 Oils from Organic orchards

A total of 14 samples from organic managed land were tested under the specified conditions. Of these, 6 samples were from Spanish orchards, 5 from Greece, 2 from Italy and 1 from Portugal. Overall, out of the 60 pesticides listed, a total of 10 were detected in at least one sample. Results per country and type of land management are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. Distribution of positives and concentration in oils from organic managed orchards

	No of samples	No of positives (% of positives)				Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
		0	1	2 – 5	> 6		
ES	6	4 (67 %)	- (-)	2 (33 %)	- (-)	0.20	0 – 0.40
GR	5	- (-)	1 (20 %)	3 (60 %)	1 (20 %)	0.20	0.10 – 1.70
IT	2	- (-)	1 (50 %)	1 (50 %)	- (-)	0.17	0.15 – 0.30
PT	1	- (-)	- (-)	1 (100 %)	- (-)	0.17	0.17-0.49
Global data	14	4 (29 %)	2 (14 %)	7 (50 %)	1 (7 %)	0.20	0 – 1.70

Having a look over the different samples and the occurrence of positive detections within them, it was found that four out of fourteen samples were free of pesticides (representing 28 % of the samples), while two of them contained at least one positive result (14 %), seven samples were in the range of 2 to 5 pesticides detected (50 %), and one of them (7 %) contained more than 6 pesticides. Overall, the median concentration of pesticides detected in ORG oils is 0.20 µg/kg, within a concentration range of 0 to 1.70 µg/kg. The distribution by percentage is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig 3. Olive oil samples (ORG soil management) with detected pesticides, arranged by country, and percentage of different detected compounds per sample

Looking at the different countries, in four of six Spanish samples (67 %) any of the target pesticides were detected, the remaining two samples (33 %) contained 2 to 5 pesticides with a median value of 0.20 µg/kg. Regarding Greek samples, one sample contained 1 pesticide (20 %), three of them contained 2 to 5 pesticides (60 %) and one sample had more than 6 pesticides (20 %), even the concentrations are not too high with a median value of 0.20 µg/kg and a concentration range from 0.10 to 1.70 µg/kg. The two Italian samples were equally distributed (50 %) with 1 pesticide and the other into the 2 to 5 gap, with a median value of 0.17 µg/kg. The Portuguese sample contained between 2 to 5 pesticides within the range of 0.17-0.49 µg/kg.

The most detected compounds were **difenoconazole, myclobutanil, and pyraclostrobin**, which are fungicides. As explained in the literature^{5,6}, pesticides exhibit dynamic behaviour in the environment; they are deposited in soils and plants and can be dispersed by rain, wind, etc. Organic soils consistently show lower levels of pesticides and contamination compared to conventional soils. However, residual contamination can still reach products and foods from organic soil management due to the dynamics of contaminants in air, water, and soil. As noted by Schleiffer *et al.* (2022)⁷, establishing a residue concentration threshold is necessary to address this behaviour. Determining whether contamination arises from pesticide misuse or cross-contamination poses a challenge in certifying food products. Thus, the presence of these compounds can be attributed to their dynamic behaviour, as their concentrations are at trace levels.

4. Discussion

A total of 41 samples were analysed under the conditions described in document *D6.9 Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)*. These samples originated from three different types of olive grove cultivation: traditional, high-density, and organic. Some of the samples were received as olive oil and the rest in the form of olives, which were extracted following methodology described in document *D6.12 Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines*. A summary of the results is presented in Table 9.

None of the samples showed positive results for Glyphosate and its metabolite. For the multiresidue pesticide analysis, differences between the oils of each type of soil management were noted. Among them, HD oils exhibited the highest contamination, followed by TD oils. As anticipated, organic oils were the least contaminated. The maximum values detected in TD and HD oils were comparable, 19 and 20 µg/kg, respectively, while organic oils recorded the highest concentration at 1.70 µg/kg. Among contaminants, the most detected were classified as fungicides (difenoconazole, myclobutanil, pyraclostrobin, and trifloxystrobin), but also the herbicide diflufenican was detected. The occurrence of fungicides may be anticipated since they are directly applied to crops. In contrast, the presence of herbicides and other types of pesticides may result from dust, soil, and environmental cross-contamination. The detected values were far below the limits set by the EU Regulation.

For Organic oils, difenoconazole, myclobutanil, and pyraclostrobin, were detected. Pesticides exhibit dynamic behaviour in the environment, being deposited in soils and plants and dispersed by various factors like rain and wind. While organic soils typically have lower pesticide levels than conventional soils, residual contamination can still affect products due to environmental dynamics. Establishing residue concentration thresholds, as suggested by Schleiffer *et al.* (2022)⁷, is essential to address this issue, yet determining the source of contamination remains challenging for certifying food products.

Essentially, the study found no major difference in pesticide levels between the control group and the group treated with biochar. A single pesticide (diflufenican) was detected in one sample from each group, but at a very low concentration (0.18 µg/kg). The other sample was free of pesticides.

Table 9. Summarized data

Glyphosate and AMPA			
Summary	Not detected in any of the tested samples		
Multiresidue analysis			
TD			
		Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
Spain (ES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50 % of samples contained 1 pesticide, the remaining 50 % contained 2 to 5 pesticides 	0.20	0.11 – 2.6
Morocco (MR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 33 % of samples with 0 pesticides detected, 33 % with 1 pesticide detected, and 33 % with 2 to 5 pesticides detected 	0.47	0 – 7.0
Italy (IT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50% of samples showed no detected pesticides, and the other 50% showed 1 detected pesticide 	0.53	0 – 0.53
Greece (GR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All 4 samples (100 %) fell within the 2 to 5 range of pesticide detection rate 	0.33	0.22 – 19
Portugal (PT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sample showed the presence of 1 pesticide 	0.17	0.17
Summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 out of 14 samples were free of pesticides (12 % of the samples) 7 samples contained at least one positive result (44 %), 7 samples had 2 to 5 pesticides detected (44 %) None of the samples contained more than 5 pesticides 	0.33	0 – 19
HD			
		Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
Spain (ES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Three of the samples (60 %) contained 1 pesticide, while 2 samples (40 %) fell within the 2 to 5 interval 	1.54	0.11 – 20
Morocco (MR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None of the selected pesticides were detected in the Moroccan samples 	-	-

Greece (GR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The only Greek sample fell within the 2 to 5 interval of pesticide detection 	0.21	0.12 – 1.30
Portugal (PT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 of them (67 %) contained 1 pesticide, and 1 sample (33 %) contained 2 to 5 pesticides 	0.41	0.15 – 18
Summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 out of 10 samples was free of pesticides (11 % of the samples) 5 samples contained at least one positive result (56 %) 3 samples had 2 to 5 pesticides detected (33 %) No sample contained more than 5 pesticides 	0.33	0 – 20
ORG			
		Median (µg/kg)	Concentration range (µg/kg)
Spain (ES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In 4 out of 6 Spanish samples (67 %), none of the target pesticides were detected. The remaining 2 samples (33 %) contained 2 to 5 pesticides 	0.20	0 – 0.40
Greece (GR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One sample contained 1 pesticide (20 %), 3 samples contained 2 to 5 pesticides (60 %), and 1 sample had more than 6 pesticides (20 %) 	0.20	0.10 – 1.70
Italy (IT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Italian samples were evenly distributed (50 %) with 1 pesticide and the other falling into the 2 to 5 range 	0.17	0.15 – 0.30
Portugal (PT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sample showed the presence of 2 to 5 pesticides 	0.17	0.17 – 0.49
Summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 out of 14 samples were free of pesticides (28 % of the samples). 2 samples contained at least one positive result (14 %). 7 samples had 2 to 5 pesticides detected (50 %). 1 sample (7 %) contained more than 6 pesticides. 	0.20	0 – 1.70

5. References

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